

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF TRENDS IN EMERGING RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF TRENDS IN EMERGING RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

Volume 4; Issue 1; 2026; Page No. 41-56

Received: 02-10-2025
Accepted: 09-12-2025
Published: 21-01-2026

The Relationship Between Principals' Leadership Styles and Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Three International Schools in Yangon, Myanmar

¹Neill Vincent Edward Conlan and ²Dr. Aye Aye Myint

¹M.Ed. Institut Brittany D'enseignement Supérieur, France

²Ph.D., Department of Educational Psychology, Graduate School of Education, The University of Tokyo

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18400354>

Corresponding Author: Neill Vincent Edward Conlan

Abstract

This study explores the relationship between principals' leadership styles and teachers' job satisfaction in three international schools in Yangon, Myanmar. The research aimed to identify the predominant leadership styles used by school principals, assess the overall level of teacher satisfaction, and examine whether a significant correlation exists between the two. Specifically, it sought to determine which leadership style most positively influences teacher job satisfaction in the context of international education.

A quantitative research approach was employed, utilizing survey data from 120 teachers across the selected schools. The findings reveal a clear positive correlation between principals' leadership styles and teachers' job satisfaction. Among the leadership styles examined, transformational leadership emerged as the most influential, showing the strongest positive association with teacher satisfaction across multiple dimensions, including support, professional development, and overall morale.

Based on these findings, it is recommended that school leaders participate in professional development programs centered on transformational leadership. Such training can enhance their ability to motivate staff, foster collaboration, and provide instructional support. Furthermore, school policies should be reviewed to ensure they promote an empowering and inclusive environment for teachers. Cultivating a school culture that values teacher input, encourages innovation, and supports continuous growth can significantly enhance job satisfaction and improve teacher retention in international school settings.

Keywords: Relationship, styles, job satisfaction, predominant, leadership

Introduction

Myanmar is a diverse country with eight major tribes. They include: 'Kachin, Kayah, Karen, Chin, Mon, Burma, Rakhine, and Shan with 135 ethnic groups and over 100 languages,' (Aung, 2020) [5]. Furthermore, it is a country with a rich history in education. In fact, 'the Southeast Asian country of Myanmar was famed for its educational achievements until the 1960s,' (Statista Research Department, 2023) [1]. Unfortunately, as of December 2023, Myanmar is listed as a least developed country by the UN (The United Nations, 2023). Moreover, the education system is ranked as '118th out of 133 countries in the Global Knowledge Index 2023,' (GLOBAL KNOWLEDGE INDEX, 2023) [14].

Although Myanmar is a developing country with an apparent below level national education system, it greatly relies on education in the both the government and private sectors. According to RFA Burmese (2023) [28], there are believed to be around 12 million students across Myanmar. Unfortunately, as the government cannot handle the burden of providing free education around the whole country to so many students; this has created opportunities in the private sector. As a result, there are a large number of international schools across the country. Prior to Covid 19, 'the international sector has attracted growing numbers of students from Myanmar's middle class, and the number of schools has mushroomed to meet this demand,' (SOE, 2018) [33].

The term 'international school' is used broadly term in Myanmar. Although there are several factors which contribute to what makes an 'international school'; such as international curricula, a multilingual and multinational student and teacher body, and international accreditation among others, (Stout, 2022) [34]. For the purpose of this study one can view an 'international school' as a school which is not solely teaching the Myanmar government curriculum and offering a curriculum from another country; 'typically three curriculum options are available: U.S., English National (British), or International Baccalaureate (IB),' (World Family Education, 2024) [36].

In the past four years, there have been a growing number of 'international schools' opening in the country's commercial capital of Yangon. This is a result of post Covid 19 business opportunities which presented a gap in the market for low cost international schools to take advantage of the political instability which is swaying students away from government schools. The Education Minister, Nyunt Pe stated that 'In June 2022, when the Ministry of Education ordered the reopening of primary, middle and high schools across the country for in-person classes for the 2022-2023 academic year, over 7 million of the country's roughly 12 million students returned to the classroom,' (RFA Burmese, 2023) [28]. This suggests that approximately 5 million students did not return to government schools,

Previously, the Myanmar Government did not have any accurate information on the collective number of students attending government, private and international schools. However, 'The Ministry of Education implemented the new Private Education Law 2023 on 12 May 2023. Furthermore, it is required for registered private schools to annually submit reports to the corresponding Regional Supervisory Board,' (International Trade Administration, 2023) [18]. This should provide more accurate statistics in the near future.

As a result of the increasing number of international schools opening in Yangon, there has been a growing demand for teachers. However, not all individuals entering the teaching profession are necessarily qualified or experienced. Many are university students-some of whom have not yet graduated-while others are entering the workforce for the first time or transitioning from different professional sectors. These shifts are largely influenced by the economic and social impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic and the ongoing political situation in Myanmar.

Despite these variations in qualification, these individuals are working in intuitions which can be classified as international schools. Moreover, all of these international schools require a principal in order to lead the whole school community, which includes students, teachers, staff, parents and other stakeholders.

The Problem Statement, Significance of the Study, Research Topic, Aims and Objectives of the Study

The Problem Statement

In the broad and diverse international school environment of Yangon; the role of principals as leaders significantly influence the overall teaching environment and educators' job satisfaction. Research shows that leadership styles have either a positive or negative impact on job satisfaction which will ultimately affect how teachers perceive their

jobs, (Febres, 2017) [12]. Furthermore, 'administrators usually adjust their leadership behavior to accomplish the mission of the organization, this could influence the teacher's job satisfaction,' (Sadasa, 2013) [31].

It is known that teachers who have low levels of job satisfaction may negatively affect student achievements. Based on research carried out in Pakistan, 'there is a modest relationship between job satisfaction and academic performance,' (IQBAL, 2016) [19].

While there have been numerous global studies which have explored the broader connection between leadership and job satisfaction such as MetLife Survey of the American Teacher; there seems to be a gap in the literature regarding the relationship of how different leadership styles adopted by school principals in international schools affect teachers' job satisfaction levels especially in the specific context of Yangon, Myanmar. To my knowledge there has never been a study carried out that covers international schools in Yangon, Myanmar. Therefore, this research will provide new insights.

Understanding the dynamics between principal leadership style and teachers job satisfaction is crucial for promoting a positive and conducive working environment and ultimately enhancing the overall quality of education in Yangon's international schools. Furthermore, addressing the issue could help to reduce teacher attrition. While exact figures on teacher turnover in Myanmar are unavailable, evidence suggests an increasing trend in workforce migration.

"More than 4 million Myanmar nationals were working abroad in 2020, according to an estimate by the International Labour Organisation, citing figures from the then-government,' (ABC Wires, 2024) [2]. This statistic reflects broader patterns of labor mobility, which may include educators seeking better opportunities overseas.

Given the growing number of international schools in Yangon and the crucial role of teachers in educational quality, addressing this gap is vital. Improved understanding of this relationship can help enhance teacher retention, instructional effectiveness, and student achievement in Myanmar's evolving private education sector.

Significance of the study

Teacher job satisfaction is a critical issue not only in developing countries like Myanmar but also globally. For example, in the USA, the results of the 2012 MetLife Survey of the American Teacher showed that 'teacher job satisfaction continues to drop to lowest level in 25 years,' (MetLife, 2012) [24]. This highlights a broader trend and underscores the importance of investigating the factors that contribute to teacher satisfaction across different educational contexts.

This study seeks to fill that gap by examining how different leadership styles adopted by school principals impact teacher job satisfaction in international schools in Yangon. The findings will provide valuable insights for policymakers, school leaders, and educators, offering guidance on leadership practices that can help foster a positive and supportive work environment.

The significance of this research lies in its originality: to the best of the researcher's knowledge, no prior study has specifically addressed this issue in the context of Yangon's

international schools. The results could serve as a foundation for further research and support evidence-based decision-making aimed at improving teacher retention and educational quality.

Research Topic

The research topic is ‘a study of the relationship between principals’ leadership styles and teachers’ job satisfaction in international schools in Yangon, Myanmar.’

Aims

This study seeks to identify and analyze various leadership styles employed by principals in international schools and examine their correlation with teachers’ job satisfaction levels.

It intends to identify which leadership style used by principals has the biggest impact on teacher job satisfaction.

Objectives

This study is required to achieve the following objectives:

1. To identify and categorize the leadership styles of principals in international schools in Yangon.
2. To assess how the teachers in these schools perceive their job satisfaction levels.
3. To analyze the correlation between principals’ leadership styles and teachers’ job satisfaction.
4. To determine which leadership style contributes the most to job satisfaction among teachers.

Research Questions

1. Which leadership styles are used by principals in international schools in Yangon?
2. How satisfied are teachers in international schools in Yangon with their jobs?
3. Is there a significant correlation between principals’ leadership styles and teachers’ job satisfaction?
4. Which leadership style contributes the most to the job satisfaction of teachers?

Section 3 – Literature Review

The purpose of this literature review is to provide an overview of common leadership styles and the concept of job satisfaction by examining relevant literature on these topics.

Job Satisfaction

The term ‘job satisfaction’ is commonly used in many sectors to describe how employees feel about their jobs. It can be defined as ‘a pleasurable emotional feeling from the appraisal of the work or job experience,’ (Colquitt, 2015) [8]. Furthermore, employees who have high job satisfaction ‘have positive feelings when they think of their job, task, duties or work,’ (Colquitt, 2015) [8].

This is supported by Northouse (2012) [25], who states that ‘job satisfaction is as a pleasure or positive feeling as a result of the value of a job or work experience.’

There are a number of reasons as to why employees feel satisfied. ‘Employees will feel satisfied if their work gives valuable results and thus, the employees will have high job satisfaction,’ (Colquitt, 2015) [8].

Employee job satisfaction is important for a number of reasons. ‘Job satisfaction is an important factor that

determines how the overall performance of the organization will be,’ (Oravee, 2018) [27]. Furthermore, ‘it involves employees’ emotional feelings, it has major consequences on their lives,’ (Buitendach, 2005) [7].

In regards to the education sector, teachers have an important responsibility in society. ‘They hold important and fundamental roles in educating and nurturing students, and in this work the teachers need to be happy and satisfied in order to be able to perform well. (Achtar, 2018) [3]. This is supported who states that ‘teachers are key facilitators of knowledge and play a vital role in building a nation’s future. It is thus particularly important to find how comfortable teachers feel in workplaces.

Furthermore, teachers’ job satisfaction is important for the education institution because ‘the happy or satisfied feeling of the teachers towards the organization affects the overall process in carrying their job, thus, contributes to the school success as a whole,’ (Sadasa, 2013) [31].

Moreover, increased job satisfaction may prevent teacher attrition because it plays an essential role in the overall commitment and productivity of the school organization. The teachers’ job satisfaction significantly influenced their commitment to the organization. Teachers who are satisfied with the job are also committed to work in the organization.

Two-Factor Theory is an excellent theory for headmasters to use in order to improve teacher job satisfaction,’ (Hamzah, 2022) [16]. According to this theory, two main factors can drive motivation are factors of satisfaction and dissatisfaction. There are a number of extrinsic factors also known as hygiene factors include compensation, work conditions, supervision, interpersonal relationships and job security.

Interpersonal includes relations between an employee and supervisors, subordinates, and peers. The category supervision involves an employee’s perspective of the supervisor.

‘If there is a satisfaction factor then a teacher will get an expected job satisfaction while if not the hygiene factor will cause job dissatisfaction.’ (Hamzah, 2022) [16] Therefore, an employee’s relationship with their supervisor and how they are being supervised may cause dissatisfaction.

This evidence suggests that teachers’ job satisfaction is influenced-either positively or negatively-by their relationship with principals and their perceptions of the principals’ leadership style.

Leadership and Leadership Styles

Leadership can be defined in many ways that is difficult to come up with a single working definition. One definition states that leadership ‘is a process whereby an individual influences a group of individuals to achieve a common goal,’ (Northouse, 2012) [25]. This is supported by Flynn who gives an almost identical definition – ‘Leadership is a process by which an individual influences colleagues towards accomplishing common goals.

However, it can be agreed that there are a number of leadership styles. Leadership Styles refers to a particular behavior applied by a leader to motivate his or her subordinates to achieve the objectives of the organization.

In order to create a positive school environment, it is important for the school principal to have positive relationships with teachers. ‘An effective leader follows a

style that helps maintain good relations with his staff,' (Hoque, 2023) [17]. Moreover, there is no one size fits all strategy as the principals chosen leadership style must be specific for their education institution. 'A school leader should use a style best suited to his teachers' behavior,' (Hoque, 2023) [17]. Therefore, an appropriate leadership style would depend on both the school's context and the maturity of the staff. Practically the school leader may have to adopt various leadership styles or change their style due to the situation, (Ali, 2017) [4]. Based on this information 'school leaders must implement various leadership styles including: 'autocratic, bureaucratic, democratic, instructional, transformational, transactional, moral, democratic, or laissez-faire leadership to achieve educational or organizational objectives,' (Hoque, 2023) [17]. On the other hand, there are suggestions that school leaders will likely have a pre-eminent leadership style which they will use more often. (Deloitte, 2022) [10].

Leadership enables organizations to be more productive and profitable, but the extent of success depends on the style of the leader and the resultant environment created for employees to function well. (Fiaz, 2017) [13].

In the course of this topic the leadership styles which will be examined are

1. Democratic
2. Instructional
3. Autocratic
4. Laissez faire
5. Transformational,
6. Transactional

Democratic Leadership

'Democratic leadership, which is also commonly known as participative leadership, is about letting multiple people participate in the decision-making process,' (Lee, 2023) [20]. Based on this definition he leadership must allow multiple people to have a voice in the decision making process. This should not only include teachers but also other stakeholders such as staff, parents, students and members of the wider community. This is further supported by research of democratic leadership styles in middle Schools of Chihuahua Mexico which states that 'In democratic approaches, decision-making authority and influence are spread throughout the school providing opportunities for all members to participate in key decisions,' (Delgado, 2014) [9]. Leaders who implement a democratic leadership style may see positive benefits among their followers. These include 'increased follower productivity, satisfaction, involvement, and commitment,' (Fiaz, 2017) [13].

Autocratic Leadership

Autocratic leadership is a classical approach in which the manager retains as much power and decision making as possible. The leader does not consult staff or allow them to give any input in the decision making process. Moreover, staff are expected to follow orders without receiving explanations. Autocratic leadership is a hierarchy in which top down commands are the routine means of communication. Furthermore, it is 'a structure in which employees must accept their leader's orders or opinions,' (Oh, 2023) [26]. This may be because the leaders do not

subordinate staff and vice versa. This is supported by Oh (2023) [26], who states that 'autocratic leadership was negatively related to organizational trust.' Furthermore, 'organizational trust positively influenced employees' job satisfaction and organizational commitment,' (Oh, 2023) [26]. It is suggested that this style of leadership should not be used when staff morale is low, high turnover, absenteeism as it can 'lead to lower motivation, higher stress, and disinterested employees, (Malec, 2022) [2].

Instructional Leadership

Instructional leaders focus on improving the quality of teaching and learning, There is evidence that this leadership style can have positive affects on the school as a whole. 'Principals' instructional leadership may support the degree to which teachers work together to improve instruction, and together leadership and teacher collaboration may contribute to school effectiveness by strengthening collective efficacy beliefs,' (Roger Goddard, 2015) [29]. There are a number of ways instructional leaders implement this leadership style in their institution. 'Instructional leaders as outstanding teachers, inspired to use their exceptional teaching skills to impact student learning. Leaders could mentor their teaching staff by observing practice, providing pointed feedback, and modeling instruction when necessary,' (LOEB, 2010) [21]. However, Loeb (2010) [21] goes on to state that this may not be practical in large institutions. The most important aspect that differentiates instructional leadership and other educational leadership is that it focuses more on the T&L process in school. (Roslizam Bin Hassan, 2019) [30]. There is evidence that the instructional leader contributes to the teacher's job satisfaction. 'The practice of headmaster leadership improves not only the school's performance and excellence but also the degree of job satisfaction among teachers,' (Hamzah, 2022) [16].

Laissez Faire

Laissez-faire is a leadership style in which the leader makes no attempt to inspire and motivate followers or to satisfy their individual needs. Furthermore, the leader gives up responsibility and allows the subordinates to make decisions by themselves. Therefore it can be viewed as avoidance leadership and could result in a lack of direction for the organization, A study by Broyles (2022) [6], showed that there is a positive correlation between laissez-faire leadership and teacher turnover. It found that 'experienced teachers who are led by laissez-faire principals are more likely to leave their job,' (Broyles, 2022) [6]. Furthermore, Broyles (2022) [6] highlighted that teachers with over three years of teaching experience are more likely to want to leave their job when led by a laissez-faire principal. This could be because 'there are no rewards or feedback to subordinates and developmental needs are left to individuals for self-management,' (Govender, 2013) [15].

Transformational Leadership

Transformational leaders 'inspire, develop, encourage and coach followers through trust and support,' (Govender, 2013) [15]. There is evidence that employees managed under a transformational leadership style displayed higher levels of job satisfaction, (Govender, 2013) [15]. Emery (2007) [11]

also came to the same conclusion. This could be because ‘employees are energized and empowered through participation to embrace an exciting and optimistic vision of the future rather than receiving personal monetary gain,’ (Govender, 2013) ^[15]. Based on this statement one can assume that transformational leaders foster intrinsic motivation among their colleagues.

Transactional Leadership

Transactional leadership is a leadership style which is very goal orientated, with structured deadlines and strict guidance. ‘It focuses on order, structure, and goal-oriented planning,’ (Martins, 2023) ^[23]. These types of leaders may tell their subordinates directly what they must do and try to motivate employees via incentives or rewards, (Martins, 2023) ^[23]. However, if they do not meet expectations they can expect to be reprimanded.

There is evidence that this type of leadership has an adverse effect on workers. ‘Employees managed under a transactional leadership style, displayed higher levels of job dissatisfaction, against associated factors such as management by exception,’ (Emery, 2007) ^[11]. This could be because everyone is motivated in different ways, some people are motivated extrinsically and others rely on intrinsic motivation. Furthermore, there is reason to believe that while teachers need both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, teachers may rely more on intrinsic motivation forces. (Scott, 2017) ^[32]. Although this leadership style may cause job dissatisfaction; Martins (2023) ^[23] states that ‘this leadership style is useful for short-term pushes or emergency situations.’

Linking Leadership Styles and Job Satisfaction

Based on the preceding discussion, it is evident that leadership styles can impact employees in various ways. Styles such as democratic, instructional, and transformational leadership are generally associated with higher levels of job satisfaction, while autocratic, laissez-faire, and transactional leadership may contribute to dissatisfaction. However, these outcomes are often context-dependent and can vary based on specific circumstances. In the following sections, this report will explore how different leadership styles influence teachers’ job satisfaction within the unique setting of international schools in Yangon.

Section 4 – Research Methodology

The purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between principals’ leadership styles and teachers’ job satisfaction in international schools in Yangon, Myanmar. This section outlines the research design and methodology used to conduct the study, including details on the population, sampling techniques, data collection methods, data analysis procedures, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This study employs quantitative research methods to examine the correlation between principals’ leadership styles and teachers’ job satisfaction at international schools, Yangon.

Population Sample: The target population for this study consists of teachers currently employed at various

international schools in Yangon, Myanmar. Given the high number of international schools in the region, a purposive sampling approach will be used to select participants from three specific schools located in different townships. For the purpose of confidentiality, these schools will be referred to as School A, School B, and School C:

- School A (Hlaing Tharyar Township)
- School B (Hlaing Township)
- School C (North Dagon Township)

Sampling Techniques

Since the total population for this study is not precisely known, a sampling method that ensures representativeness and minimizes bias is necessary. Therefore, simple random sampling will be employed to select a subset of participants from the larger population of teachers in international schools in Yangon. This method is chosen because it gives each individual an equal chance of being selected, thereby enhancing the reliability and generalizability of the findings. Data collection Method.

Data will be collected through self-administered web-based surveys. This method has been selected for several reasons. First, it is cost-effective, as surveys can be distributed online at no financial cost. Second, identical questionnaires can be sent to multiple participants, allowing them to respond at their own convenience without the need for the researcher’s physical presence. Additionally, platforms such as LinkedIn will be utilized to reach members of the target population more effectively.

The survey instrument will be quantitative in nature, employing a five-point Likert scale to measure participants’ beliefs, attitudes, and opinions related to leadership styles and job satisfaction.

Data Analysis Techniques

To gain meaningful insights from the collected data, descriptive and correlational analysis will be employed. Descriptive statistics will be used to present the current state of affairs-specifically, to identify the predominant leadership styles practiced by principals and to assess the job satisfaction levels of teachers. Correlational analysis, on the other hand, will be used to examine the relationship between these two variables. This combination of methods will provide a comprehensive understanding of how leadership styles may influence teachers’ job satisfaction within international schools in Yangon.

Section 5 – Presentation of Analysis and Findings

This section presents the analysis of data collected from the survey conducted for the study titled "A Study of the Relationship between *Principals’* Leadership Styles and Teachers’ Job Satisfaction in International Schools in Yangon."

The analysis is divided into three main parts: (1) the demographic characteristics of the respondents, (2) the leadership styles of principals as perceived by teachers, and (3) the levels of teachers’ job satisfaction.

For this study, data were collected from three international schools located in different townships of Yangon: Hlaing Tharyar, Hlaing, and North Dagon. To maintain anonymity and ensure consistency in reporting, these schools are referred to as School A (Hlaing Tharyar), School B

(Hlaing), and School C (North Dagon).

Demographic Profile Analysis

This section presents the frequency distribution of respondents according to various demographic variables. The demographic characteristics analyzed include job status, gender, nationality, job role, school location, years of teaching experience in international schools, current educational level taught, and the length of time working under the current principal. This analysis provides context for understanding the background of the participants and supports interpretation of the subsequent findings related to leadership styles and job satisfaction.

Gender position

Table (1) presents the analysis of the respondents' gender distribution. Participants were asked to indicate their gender by selecting either "male" or "female."

Table 1: The Gender of Respondents

Gender of Respondents				
Gender of Respondent	School A	School B	School C	Total
Female	33	34	40	107
Male	7	6	0	13
Total	40	40	40	120

Based on the data presented in Table (1), the gender distribution of respondents reveals that 10.83% were male, whereas 89.17% were female. This indicates that female participants constituted a significantly larger proportion of the sample.

All three schools demonstrated a predominance of female teachers. School A had the highest proportion of male teachers at 53.85%, followed by School B with 46.15%. In contrast, School C reported no male teachers, indicating a complete female representation among its teaching staff.

Nationality Analysis

Table (2) presents an analysis of the respondents' nationality. Participants were asked to indicate whether they are Myanmar or Non-Myanmar.

Table 2: The Nationality of Respondents

Nationality of Respondents				
Nationality	School 1	School 2	School 3	Total
Myanmar	33	31	40	104
Non-Myanmar	7	9	0	16
Total	40	40	40	120

As illustrated in Table (2), the majority of teachers across all three schools were Myanmar nationals, accounting for 86.67% of the total respondents. The remaining 13.33% were non-Myanmar nationals.

Among the non-Myanmar participants (n = 16), School B had the highest representation with 56.25%, followed by School A with 43.75%. Notably, School C had no 'non-Myanmar' teachers.

Position of Respondents

Table (3) is the analysis of position of respondents. Participants were asked to describe their current position at their school. They were required to indicate whether they are 'assistant teachers' who support the lead teacher, 'class

teachers' who teach multiple subjects to one or more grade levels, or 'subject teachers' who specialize in a specific subject.

Table 3: The Position of Respondents

Position of respondents				
Position	School A	School B	School C	Total
Assistant Teacher	14	22	0	36
Class Teacher	13	9	30	52
Subject Teacher	13	9	10	32
Total	40	40	40	120

As shown in Table (3), the distribution of job roles among respondents indicates that assistant teachers, who support lead teachers, comprise 30% of the sample. Class teachers, responsible for teaching multiple subjects across one or more grade levels, represent 43.33%, while subject teachers, who specialize in specific subjects, account for 26.67%. Thus, 'class teachers' constitute the largest group of respondents in this study.

Respondents from Each International School

Table (4) presents the distribution of respondents' from each international school, School A, School B, and School C.

Table 4: The Respondents from Each International School

Townships of International Schools		
Township	Respondents	Percentage
School A	40	33.33%
School B	40	33.33%
School C	40	33.33%
Total	120	100%

From the data displayed in Table (4), the township distribution of respondents indicates that 33.33% are from School A, 33.33% from School B, and 33.33% from School C. This shows that the proportion of respondents are evenly distributed across the three schools, with each contributing an equal share to the overall sample.

Length of Time Respondents Have Been Teaching at International Schools:

Respondents were asked how long they have been teaching at international schools. The following options were provided: Less than 1 year, 1-3 years, 4-6 years, and over 10 years. The data reveals the distribution of teaching experience among the respondents. Table (5) displays the number of respondents and the corresponding percentage for each category of years of teaching experience at international schools.

Table 5: Length of Time Respondents Have Been Teaching at International Schools

Years of Teaching Experience at international school	School A	School B	School C	Total
Less than one year	0	16	0	16
1-3	13	18	0	31
4-6	7	3	20	30
6-10	13	0	20	33
Over 10 Years	7	3	0	10

This table 5 illustrates the distribution of respondents' teaching experience at international schools, highlighting the variety of experience levels among the participants.

School B has the highest proportion of teachers with less than one year of experience with 13.3%. In contrast, School A and School B have the majority of their staff (25.8%) in the 1–3 years’ experience range, with School C having none. Mid-level experience (4–6 years) is most prominent in School C with 66.7%, whereas School A and B contribute less. Similarly, the 6–10 years bracket is dominated by School A and School C, each contributing 39.4% and 60.6% respectively of the 33 teachers in this group. Only School A and B have teachers with over 10 years of experience, with School A accounting for 70% of this group. Overall, School C has the most experienced staff (predominantly 4–10 years), while School B has the least experienced cohort.

Grade Level Taught by Respondents

Respondents were asked to indicate the grade levels they teach at international schools, with the options including Kindergarten (KG), Elementary, Middle School, and High School. Respondents could select multiple grade levels if applicable therefore the total is higher than n=120. Table (6) presents the distribution of grade levels taught by the respondents.

Table 6: Grade Levels Taught by Respondents

Grade Level Taught				
Grade Level	School A	School B	School C	Total
Kindergarten	7	28	20	55
Elementary	13	18	30	61
Middle School	20	0	0	20
High School	0	0	0	0

This table 6 shows the distribution of grade levels taught by the respondents, reflecting the variety of educational stages represented among the teachers at international schools. Out of a total of 136 responses, 61 (44.9%) are assigned to the elementary level, making it the most common teaching level across the schools. This is followed by 55 teachers (40.4%) in kindergarten, and 20 teachers (14.7%) in middle school. No teachers (0%) are assigned to the high school level, indicating that none of the schools currently offer high school education. School C employs the highest number of elementary teachers (30), representing 49.2% of all elementary teachers, while School B contributes 29.5% (18 teachers), and School A accounts for 21.3% (13 teachers). For kindergarten, School B employs the majority (28 teachers or 50.9%), followed by School C with 36.4% (20 teachers), and School A with 12.7% (7 teachers). All 20 middle school teachers (100%) are from School A, with Schools B and C reporting none. These figures highlight the emphasis placed on early childhood and elementary education across the schools, with School A being the only institution offering middle school education. The absence of high school-level teaching staff suggests that these schools currently operate only up to the middle school level. Such distribution is critical for analyzing the influence of leadership styles and job satisfaction, as teaching responsibilities and institutional focus vary significantly by grade level. Length of Time Working with Current Principal Respondents were asked how long they have been working with their current principal. The following options were provided: Less than 1 year, 1–2 years, 3–4 years, and more

than 5 years. The responses indicate the range of experience respondents have had with their current principal. Table (7) presents the distribution of the length of time respondents have worked with their current principal.

Table 7: The Length of Time Working with Current Principal

Length of Time Working with Current Principal				
Duration with Current Principal	School A	School B	School C	Total
Less than 1 year	6	31	0	37
1-2 Years	7	9	10	26
3-4 Years	27	0	20	47
Over 5 Years	0	0	10	10

This table illustrates the distribution of the length of time respondents have worked with their current principal, highlighting the varying levels of familiarity and experience with leadership among the participants.

The data on the duration respondents have worked with their current principals reveals notable differences among the three schools. Most teachers 39.2% have worked with their current principal for 3–4 years, with significant representation from Schools A and C. A smaller group of 26 respondents (21.7%) reported working with their principal for 1–2 years, indicating relatively recent leadership changes or appointments. 37 respondents (30.8%), predominantly from School B, have worked with their current principal for less than 1 year, suggesting a very recent change in leadership or principal turnover at that school. Interestingly, 10 respondents (8.3%), all from School C, have been with the same principal for over 5 years, pointing to leadership stability in that context. These findings suggest that School B is experiencing a phase of new leadership, while School C demonstrates strong leadership continuity, and School A, falls somewhere in between, with a majority of its staff having 3–4 years of experience with their current principal.

The leadership styles of principals

Section 2 of the questionnaire presents the findings related to the leadership styles of school principals Participants were asked to rate their level of agreement with a number of statements describing their principal’s leadership style using a five-point Likert scale, where 1 indicated "strongly disagree" and 5 indicated "strongly agree."

Statement (1)

The table 8 below shows the responses to the statement ‘My principal encourages collaboration and shared decision making among staff members.’

Table 8: Response to the Statement ‘My principal encourages collaboration and shared decision making among staff members’

My principal encourages collaboration and shared decision making among staff members				
Likert Scale Response	School A	School B	School C	Total
1. Strongly Disagree	0	3	20	23
2. Disagree	27	0	20	47
3. Neutral	7	0	0	7
4. Agree	6	12	0	8
5. Strongly Agree	0	25	0	25

The responses to the statement "My principal encourages collaboration and shared decision making among staff members" reveal significant contrasts across the three schools. In School A, the majority of respondents (27 out of 40, or 67.5%) disagreed with the statement, with another 7 (17.5%) remaining neutral, indicating limited perceived collaboration. Similarly, School C had 20 respondents (51.3%) who disagreed and another 20 (51.3%) who strongly disagreed, showing a strong lack of confidence in collaborative leadership. In stark contrast, all respondents in School B provided positive feedback with 25 (62.5%) strongly agreed and 12 (30%) agreed, totaling 92.5% of responses in favor.

Statement (2)

Respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement with the statement: "The principal values teachers' input and seeks to involve them in key decisions." The table 9 below presents the distribution of responses based on the five-point Likert scale.

Table 9: Response to the statement 'The principal values teachers' input and seeks to involve them in key decisions'

The principal values teachers' input and seeks to involve them in key decisions.				
Likert Scale Response	School A	School B	School C	Total
1- Strongly Disagree	14	0	20	34
2 – Disagree	13	0	10	23
3 – Neutral	13	9	10	32
4 – Agree	0	22	0	22
5 – Strongly Agree	0	9	0	9

Table (10) presents the distribution of teacher responses regarding the statement, "The principal values teachers' input and seeks to involve them in key decisions," using a five-point Likert scale.

The data reveals that a significant portion of teachers-34 respondents (28.3%)-strongly disagreed, and another 23 (19.2%) disagreed, amounting to 47.5% who hold negative perceptions of principal involvement in decision-making. These responses were concentrated in School A and School C, with 14 and 20 teachers respectively selecting "strongly disagree," and 13 and 10 selecting "disagree." In contrast, School B had no respondents in either of the disagreement categories, highlighting a notable divergence in leadership perceptions across the schools. Additionally, 32 teachers (26.7%) selected neutral, indicating a moderate level of uncertainty or disengagement with this leadership aspect. School B stood out positively, with 22 teachers (73.3% of its sample) agreeing and 9 (30%) strongly agreeing, while Schools A and C had no teachers expressing agreement or strong agreement.

Overall, only 25.8% of respondents across all schools expressed a positive view (agree or strongly agree) regarding their principal's efforts to involve teachers in key decisions. This contrast suggests that while School B appears to foster an inclusive and participative leadership culture, Schools A and C may be experiencing leadership gaps that hinder teacher involvement.

Statement (3)

Respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement

with the statement: "My principal focuses on improving teaching and learning outcomes in the school." The table below presents the distribution of responses using a five-point Likert scale.

Table 10: Response to the statement 'My principal focuses on improving teaching and learning outcomes in the school'

My principal focuses on improving teaching and learning outcomes in the school				
Likert Scale Response	School A	School B	School C	Total
1- Strongly Disagree	7	0	10	17
2 – Disagree	7	0	0	7
3 – Neutral	20	0	20	40
4 – Agree	6	15	10	31
5 – Strongly Agree	0	25	0	25

Responses to the statement "My principal focuses on improving teaching and learning outcomes in the school" show strong variation across the three schools. As shown in Table (11), School B stands out with entirely positive feedback-15 respondents (37.5%) agreed and 25 (62.5%) strongly agreed, totaling 100% in favor. In contrast, perceptions in School A are mixed, with 35% (14 out of 40) expressing disagreement (strongly disagree or disagree), and 50% (20 respondents) remaining neutral. Only 6 respondents (15%) agreed, and none strongly agreed. Similarly, in School C, half of the respondents (20 out of 40) remained neutral, while 10 (25%) strongly disagreed and 10 (25%) agreed. These results suggest that School B's leadership is viewed most favorably in terms of its focus on improving teaching and learning, while Schools A and C exhibit greater uncertainty or dissatisfaction in this area.

Statement (4)

Respondents were asked to rate their agreement with the statement: "The principal provides guidance and support on instructional matters." The table below displays the distribution of responses based on a five-point Likert scale.

Table 11: Response to the statement 'The principal provides guidance and support on instructional matters'

The principal provides guidance and support on instructional matters				
Likert Scale Response	School A	School B	School C	Total
1. Strongly Disagree	0	0	0	0
2. Disagree	13	0	10	23
3. Neutral	13	3	30	46
4. Agree	7	17	0	24
5. Strongly Agree	7	20	0	27

The responses to the statement "The principal provides guidance and support on instructional matters" indicate a generally positive perception among teachers across the three schools.

Based on Table (11), a majority of respondents expressed agreement, with 27 (22.5%) strongly agreeing and 24 (20%) agreeing, totaling 42.5% of all responses. Notably, School B exhibited the highest concentration of positive responses, with 37 out of 40 respondents either agreeing or strongly agreeing. In contrast, School C showed a more neutral to negative trend, with 30 respondents selecting 'Neutral' and 10 selecting 'Disagree', and none expressing agreement.

School A displayed a balanced distribution across response categories, suggesting a more varied perception of the principal’s instructional support.

Overall, the results suggest a divergence in perceived principal support among schools, with stronger instructional leadership reported in School B and more uncertainty or dissatisfaction evident in School C.

Statement (5)

Respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement with the statement: ‘The principal makes most of the decisions without consulting staff members.’ The table 12 below presents the distribution of responses on a five-point Likert scale.

Table 12: Response to the statement ‘The principal makes most of the decisions without consulting staff members’

The principal makes most of the decisions without consulting staff members				
Likert Scale Response	School A	School B	School C	Total
1. Strongly Disagree	0	15	10	25
2. Disagree	0	18	0	18
3. Neutral	20	0	20	40
4. Agree	13	7	10	30
5. Strongly Agree	7	0	0	7

The statement “the principal makes most of the decisions without consulting staff members” reveal varied perceptions of leadership inclusion across the three schools. In School B, most respondents disagreed with the statement, with 33 out of 40 selecting "Strongly Disagree" or "Disagree", indicating a strong sense of participative decision-making. Conversely, School C showed a more divided outlook, with 20 respondents neutral and 10 agreeing, suggesting uncertainty or mixed experiences regarding staff involvement. School A reflected a nuanced view, with a high number of neutral responses (20) and 13 in agreement, indicating moderate concerns about top-down decision-making. Only 7 respondents across all schools strongly agreed with the statement, suggesting that while some teachers do perceive a lack of consultation, the overall trend points toward varying but not overwhelmingly negative perceptions of leadership inclusiveness.

Statement (6)

Respondents were asked to express their level of agreement with the statement: “The principal provides minimal guidance or supervision, allowing teachers to make most decisions on their own.” The table 13 below presents the distribution of responses based on a five-point Likert scale.

Table 13: Response to the statement ‘The principal provides minimal guidance or supervision, allowing teachers to make most decisions on their own’

The principal provides minimal guidance or supervisor, allowing teachers to make most decisions on their own.				
Likert Scale Response	School A	School B	School C	Total
1. Strongly Disagree	0	3	10	13
2. Disagree	13	9	10	32
3. Neutral	20	12	0	32
4. Agree	7	9	20	36
5. Strongly Agree	0	7	0	7

Analysis of the statement “The principal provides minimal guidance or supervision, allowing teachers to make most decisions on their own” revealed a relatively balanced distribution of perceptions among the three schools.

Based on Table (14), approximately 36% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed with the statement, indicating a perception of principal leadership that favors teacher autonomy. Conversely, 37.5% of teachers disagreed or strongly disagreed, suggesting a view of more directive or involved leadership practices. Notably, School C demonstrated the highest proportion of agreement, reflecting a stronger perception of principal non-intervention. In contrast, responses from School A were predominantly neutral, while School B exhibited the greatest variation in responses, including the highest incidence of strong agreement. These findings underscore the variability in leadership styles and their perception across institutional contexts.

Statement (7)

Respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement with the statement: “The principal tends to avoid getting involved in day-to-day teaching activities.” The table 14 below displays the distribution of responses based on a five-point Likert scale.

Table 14: Response to the statement ‘The principal tends to avoid getting involved in day to day teaching activities’

The principal tends to avoid getting involved in day to day teaching activities				
Likert Scale Response	School A	School B	School C	Total
1- Strongly Disagree	0	25	0	25
2 – Disagree	13	9	0	22
3 – Neutral	27	6	10	43
4 – Agree	0	0	30	30
5 – Strongly Agree	0	0	0	0

Based on Table (15), responses were divided, with 25 respondents (20.8%) strongly disagreeing and 22 (18.3%) disagreeing, indicating that a significant portion believed their principals were actively involved in daily teaching matters. Meanwhile, 43 respondents (35.8%) chose a neutral stance, and 30 respondents (25%) agreed, suggesting that perceptions were mixed or uncertain. Notably, no respondents strongly agreed, highlighting a lack of strong consensus supporting the view that principals avoid daily involvement. School B had the highest number of “Strongly Disagree” responses (25), while School C stood out with all 30 “Agree” responses, implying differing perceptions of leadership involvement across the schools. School A leaned toward neutrality and disagreement, with no respondents agreeing. These patterns reflect a notable discrepancy in how principals' engagement in daily teaching activities is perceived among different schools.

Statement (8)

Respondents were asked to express their level of agreement with the statement: “My principal inspires and motivates teachers to achieve higher levels of performance.” The table below shows the distribution of responses based on a five-point Likert scale.

Table 15: Response to the statement ‘My principal inspires and motivates teachers to achieve higher levels of performance’

My principal inspires and motivates teachers to achieve higher levels of performance.				
Likert Scale Response	School A	School B	School C	Total
1. Strongly Disagree	0	0	10	10
2. Disagree	13	0	0	13
3. Neutral	0	0	30	30
4. Agree	20	12	0	32
5. Strongly Agree	7	28	0	35

Based on Table (15), overall, 32 respondents (26.7%) agreed and 35 (29.2%) strongly agreed, indicating that 55.9% of participants viewed their principals as motivating leaders. On the other hand, 10 respondents (8.3%) strongly disagreed, and 13 (10.8%) disagreed, while a notable portion-30 respondents (25%)-chose a neutral position. School B had the highest number of “Strongly Agree” responses (28), reflecting a highly positive perception among its staff. In contrast, School C showed no positive responses and the highest neutrality (30), along with all 10 “Strongly Disagree” responses, suggesting a more critical or disengaged view. School A showed a mixed pattern, with both disagreement (13) and agreement (20), indicating some division in perception. These results reflect significant variations in leadership perceptions across schools.

Statement (9)

Respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement with the statement: “The principal encourages innovative teaching methods and promotes professional development.” The table 16 below presents the distribution of responses based on a five-point Likert scale.

Table 16: Response to the statement ‘The Principal Encourages Innovative Teaching Methods and Promotes Professional Development’

The principal encourages innovative teaching methods and promotes professional development				
Likert Scale Response	School A	School B	School C	Total
1. Strongly Disagree	0	0	0	0
2. Disagree	13	0	0	13
3. Neutral	7	6	20	33
4. Agree	20	9	20	49
5. Strongly Agree	0	25	0	25

For this statement, the majority of participants expressed positive perceptions, with 40.8% agreeing and 20.8% strongly agreeing, totaling 61.6% in favor. A smaller portion, 27.5%, selected a neutral response, indicating some ambivalence or lack of strong opinion. Only 10.8% disagreed, and no respondents strongly disagreed. These findings suggest that most respondents perceive their principals as supportive of innovation and professional growth within their schools.

Statement (10)

Respondents were asked to express their level of agreement with the statement: “The principal focuses on maintaining order and structure through rewards and punishments.” The table 17 below shows the distribution of responses based on a five-point Likert scale.

Table 17: Response to the statement ‘The principal focuses on maintaining order and structure in the school through rewards and punishment’

The principal focuses on maintaining order and structure in the school through rewards and punishment				
Likert Scale Response	School A	School B	School C	Total
1. Strongly Disagree	0	9	10	19
2. Disagree	13	3	20	36
3. Neutral	7	19	10	36
4. Agree	13	6	0	19
5. Strongly Agree	7	3	0	10

Respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement with the statement, “The principal focuses on maintaining order and structure in the school through rewards and punishments.” Based on Table (17), responses were mixed, with 36 respondents (30%) choosing “Disagree” and another 36 (30%) selecting “Neutral,” indicating uncertainty or disagreement with this approach. A smaller portion-19 respondents (15.8%)-agreed, while only 10 (8.3%) strongly agreed, suggesting limited strong support for the use of rewards and punishments as a dominant strategy. Meanwhile, 19 respondents (15.8%) strongly disagreed, reinforcing the divided perception. School A had the most balanced distribution, including both support (13 “Agree” and 7 “Strongly Agree”) and disagreement (13 “Disagree”). School B leaned toward neutrality, with 19 neutral responses, while School C was characterized by high disagreement (20 “Disagree” and 10 “Strongly Disagree”) and no agreement at all. These results suggest that while some support for structured behavior management exists, there is considerable variability across schools and a general lack of strong consensus authorizing the practice.

Statement (11)

Respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement with the statement: “The principal clearly outlines expectations for teachers and provides rewards for meeting them.” The table 18 below presents the distribution of responses based on a five-point Likert scale.

Table 18: Response to the statement ‘The principal clearly outlines expectations for teachers and provides rewards for meeting them’

The principal clearly outlines expectations for teachers and provides rewards for meeting them				
Likert Scale Response	School A	School B	School C	Total
1. Strongly Disagree	7	6	10	23
2. Disagree	7	6	30	43
3. Neutral	26	12	0	38
4. Agree	0	10	0	10
5. Strongly Agree	0	6	0	6

Respondents rated their agreement with the statement, “The principal clearly outlines expectations for teachers and provides rewards for meeting them.” Based on Table (18), the responses indicate a predominantly negative or uncertain perception, with 43 respondents (35.8%) disagreeing and 23 (19.2%) strongly disagreeing, making up over half (55%) of the total. 38 respondents (31.7%) remained neutral, while

only a small minority-10 (8.3%) agreed and 6 (5%) strongly agreed-expressed positive views. School C showed the strongest negative perception, with 30 “Disagree” and 10 “Strongly Disagree” responses, and no agreement. School A’s responses were mostly neutral (26), with some disagreement, while School B showed the most balanced spread, including the only “Strongly Agree” responses (6) and a modest number of agreements (10). These results suggest a general lack of clarity or effectiveness in how principals communicate expectations and recognize teacher performance, particularly in School C.

Teachers Job Satisfaction

This section evaluates teachers' levels of satisfaction across various dimensions of their professional experience. Participants were asked to indicate their satisfaction with specific aspects of their job using a five-point Likert scale, where 1 represents *Very Dissatisfied* and 5 represents *Very Satisfied*.

Statement (1)

Teachers were asked to assess their overall satisfaction with their teaching experience by rating their satisfaction with overall teaching experience. The distribution of responses is summarized in the table 19 below.

Table 19: Distribution of Teachers’ ‘Satisfaction with Overall Teaching Experience’

Satisfaction with Overall Teaching Experience				
Satisfaction Level	School A	School B	School C	Total
1. Very Dissatisfied	0	0	0	0
2. Dissatisfied	0	3	0	3
3. Neutral	20	9	10	39
4. Satisfied	20	22	30	72
5. Very Satisfied	0	6	0	6

The data in Table (19) indicates generally positive levels of satisfaction among teachers across all three schools. A significant majority of respondents (60%) reported being “Satisfied” with their overall teaching experience, with School C contributing the highest number of satisfied responses (30). Additionally, 6 teachers (5%) from School B reported being “Very Satisfied,” making it the only school with responses in this highest satisfaction category. Neutral responses totaled 39 (32.5%), suggesting a substantial portion of teachers feel neither satisfied nor dissatisfied. Only a small minority (3 respondents, all from School B) indicated dissatisfaction, and no respondents selected “Very Dissatisfied.” These findings suggest a broadly favorable sentiment regarding teaching experience, particularly in Schools B and C, with limited expressions of discontent.

Statement (2)

Teachers were asked to assess their satisfaction with professional development opportunities. The distribution of responses is summarized in the table 20 below.

Table 20: Distribution of Teachers’ ‘Satisfaction with Professional Development Opportunities’

Satisfaction with Professional Development Opportunities				
Satisfaction Level	School A	School B	School C	Total
1- Very Dissatisfied	0	3	0	3
2 – Dissatisfied	20	6	0	26
3 – Neutral	0	6	10	16
4 - Satisfied	20	18	20	58
5 – Very Satisfied	0	6	0	6

The data from Table (20) reveal a predominantly positive trend. A combined 64 respondents (64%) indicated they were either “Satisfied” or “Very Satisfied,” with School C and School Beach contributing significantly (20 and 24 positive responses respectively). However, 26 respondents (26%) expressed dissatisfaction, the majority of whom were from School A (20). School A exhibited a polarized response pattern, with no participants selecting “Neutral,” suggesting strong opinions-either satisfied or dissatisfied. Meanwhile, School B was the only school with “Very Dissatisfied” responses (3) and all 6 “Very Satisfied” responses, indicating mixed perceptions. Neutral responses totaled 16, with School C contributing the highest share (10).

Overall, while the majority of teachers express satisfaction with the professional development offered, noticeable dissatisfaction in School A highlights the need for targeted improvements.

Statement (3)

Teachers were asked to assess their satisfaction with the support received from their principal. The distribution of responses is summarized in the table 21 below.

Table 21: Distribution of Teachers’ ‘Satisfaction with Support from Principal’

Satisfaction with Support from Principal				
Satisfaction Level	School A	School B	School C	Total
1. Very Dissatisfied	7	3	10	20
2. Dissatisfied	0	3	0	3
3. Neutral	20	6	20	40
4. Satisfied	7	9	0	16
5. Very Satisfied	0	21	10	31

The results from Table (21) show a mixed perception among teachers regarding the level of support received from their principals. A substantial proportion (31 out of 110 respondents; 28%) reported being “Very Satisfied,” with School B contributing the highest number (21) and School C contributing 10. Conversely, 20 teachers (18%) expressed they were “Very Dissatisfied,” with School C accounting for half of those responses (10), indicating strong dissatisfaction in that context. Additionally, 40 respondents (36%) selected “Neutral,” suggesting a significant group with ambivalent views. Notably, School A had the highest number of neutral responses (20) but no respondents expressing “Very Satisfied.” Meanwhile, only 16

respondents (15%) reported being “Satisfied,” and dissatisfaction remained relatively low at 3 total responses. Overall, the data reflect a divided perception of principal support, with School B demonstrating the most favorable results and School A showing more moderate or indifferent sentiment.

Statement (4)

Teachers were asked to assess their satisfaction with their relationships with colleagues. The distribution of responses is summarized in the table 22 below.

Table 22: Distribution of Teachers’ Satisfaction with Relationships with Colleagues

Satisfaction with Colleague Relationships				
Satisfaction Level	School A	School B	School C	Total
1. Very Dissatisfied	0	0	0	0
2. Dissatisfied	0	0	0	0
3. Neutral	7	6	0	13
4. Satisfied	27	25	40	92
5. Very Satisfied	6	9	0	15

The data indicate a consistently high level of satisfaction among teachers regarding their relationships with colleagues across all three schools. A significant 84% of respondents (92 out of 110) reported being “Satisfied,” with School C leading (40 responses), followed by School A (27) and School B (25). An additional 15 respondents (14%) reported being “Very Satisfied,” notably with School B contributing the highest at 9 responses. Only 13 respondents (12%) selected “Neutral,” and none reported dissatisfaction in any form. These findings suggest a strong collegial environment across all institutions, with particularly high satisfaction observed at School C and School B.

Statement (5)

This section assesses teachers’ satisfaction with the work-life balance supported or enabled by their school. Respondents rated their satisfaction on a five-point Likert scale, where 1 indicates Very Dissatisfied and 5 indicates Very Satisfied.

Table 23: Distribution of Teachers’ Satisfaction with Work-Life Balance

Teachers’ Satisfaction with Work-Life Balance				
Satisfaction Level	School A	School B	School C	Total
1. Very Dissatisfied	7	0	0	7
2. Dissatisfied	7	0	0	7
3. Neutral	7	9	10	26
4. Satisfied	20	12	20	52
5. Very Satisfied	0	18	10	28

The data indicate that the majority of teachers reported a positive level of satisfaction with their work-life balance. Specifically, 80 out of 120 respondents (67%) expressed being either “Satisfied” (52) or “Very Satisfied” (28). School B had the highest number of teachers selecting “Very Satisfied” (18), followed by School C (10), while School A had no teachers in this highest satisfaction category. A moderate 26 teachers (22%) selected “Neutral,” reflecting ambivalence. Conversely, 14 teachers (11%), all from School A, reported being either “Dissatisfied” or

“Very Dissatisfied,” indicating that dissatisfaction with work-life balance is localized. These findings suggest generally favorable perceptions of work-life balance, albeit with notable school-level variation, particularly in School A.

Statement (6)

This section explores teachers’ perceptions of the opportunities available to them for career advancement within their current educational setting. Respondents were asked to rate their level of satisfaction using a five-point Likert scale, where 1 represents Very Dissatisfied and 5 represents Very Satisfied.

Table 24: Distribution of Teachers’ Satisfaction with Opportunities for Career Advancement

Satisfaction with Career Advancement Opportunities				
Satisfaction Level	School A	School B	School C	Total
1. Very Dissatisfied	0	0	0	0
2. Dissatisfied	7	6	0	13
3. Neutral	13	9	10	32
4. Satisfied	13	12	30	55
5. Very Satisfied	7	12	0	19

The data reveal a generally positive perception of career advancement opportunities among teachers across the three schools. A combined 74 out of 120 teachers (62%) reported being either “Satisfied” (55) or “Very Satisfied” (19). School C showed the strongest positive sentiment, with 30 teachers indicating satisfaction, though notably, none expressed being “Very Satisfied.” In contrast, School B had a more favorable distribution with 12 responses in both “Satisfied” and “Very Satisfied” categories. Meanwhile, School A had the broadest spread across satisfaction levels, including the only responses in the “Dissatisfied” category (7). Neutral responses were significant at 32 teachers (27%), suggesting room for clearer or more consistent advancement pathways. Overall, while perceptions are predominantly positive, disparities across schools-especially in terms of high satisfaction-may reflect differing institutional support or opportunity structures.

Statement (7)

This section provides an overview of teachers’ overall satisfaction with their job. Respondents were asked to evaluate their general job satisfaction using a five-point Likert scale, where 1 indicates Very Dissatisfied and 5 indicates Very Satisfied.

Table 25: Distribution of Teachers’ Overall Job Satisfaction

Overall Job Satisfaction				
Satisfaction Level	School A	School B	School C	Total
1. Very Dissatisfied	0	0	0	0
2. Dissatisfied	7	6	0	13
3. Neutral	13	9	10	32
4. Satisfied	13	12	30	55
5. Very Satisfied	7	12	0	19

The data reveal that a substantial majority of teachers reported positive overall job satisfaction. Specifically, 74 out of 120 respondents (62%) selected either “Satisfied” or “Very Satisfied,” with School C having the highest proportion of satisfied teachers (30) but no respondents

indicating being “Very Satisfied.” In contrast, School B had the highest number of “Very Satisfied” responses (12), followed by School A (7). A neutral stance was expressed by 32 teachers (27%), while a small minority-13 teachers (11%)-reported being “Dissatisfied.” Notably, no

participants selected “Very Dissatisfied” across any school. These findings suggest generally favorable perceptions of job satisfaction, with variation in intensity across institutions.

Fig 1: Bar chart displaying the Leadership Averages

Fig 2: Bar chart displaying the Satisfaction Averages

Fig 3: A correlation heatmap showing how leadership styles relate to job satisfaction

The correlation heatmap generated from the merged leadership and job satisfaction data provides key insights into the relationship between principals' leadership styles and teachers' job satisfaction in international schools in Yangon. Notably, transformational leadership traits-such as encouraging collaboration, valuing teacher input, and inspiring higher levels of performance-demonstrate moderate to strong positive correlations with various facets of job satisfaction, including overall satisfaction, professional development opportunities, and support from the principal. This indicates that when school leaders adopt participative and motivational approaches, teachers tend to report higher satisfaction levels. In contrast, leadership behaviors associated with autocratic or laissez-faire styles-such as unilateral decision-making and lack of involvement in teaching activities-exhibit weak or negative correlations with job satisfaction metrics. These results suggest that such approaches may be less effective in promoting a positive working environment for teachers. Overall, these findings suggest that transformational leadership has the most substantial influence on teacher satisfaction in Yangon's international schools, highlighting the importance of supportive, empowering leadership in promoting teacher well-being and retention.

Section 6: Presentation of Solutions and Recommendations

In summary, this study found that transformational leadership style is strongly associated with higher levels of teacher satisfaction. These findings highlight the importance of school leaders adopting practices that inspire, motivate, and engage teachers in shaping a shared and successful future for their schools.

Therefore, it is recommended that professional development programs be implemented to equip principals with the skills and competencies necessary to practice transformational leadership effectively.

Additionally, school policies should be revised to emphasize the development and reinforcement of a clear vision and mission. These elements play a crucial role in defining institutional goals and fostering a collaborative school culture where teachers feel valued, empowered, and committed to continuous improvement.

Limitations of the study

While this study provides valuable insights into the leadership style that positively influences teachers' job satisfaction, it is important to acknowledge its limitations. The research was limited to three international schools located in Yangon, Myanmar. As a result, the findings may not be fully generalizable to all international schools across the country or to other educational contexts.

Recommendations for Future Research

To build upon the findings of this study and address its limitations, future research should include a larger and more diverse sample of international schools, extending beyond Yangon to other major cities such as Mandalay and Nay Pyi Taw. Additionally, future studies should explore potential differences in job satisfaction between male and female teachers, as well as between Myanmar and non-Myanmar (expatriate) teachers. These comparisons could provide

deeper insights into how demographic and cultural factors may interact with leadership styles to influence teacher satisfaction.

References

1. Statista Research Department. Education in Myanmar. Statista [Internet]; c2023 [cited 2024 Feb 10]. Available from: <https://www.statista.com/topics/5813/education-in-myanmar/>
2. ABC Wires. Myanmar bans men from applying to work abroad as junta looks to boost military numbers. ABC News [Internet]; c2024. Available from: <https://www.abc.net.au/news/2024-05-04/myanmar-junta-bans-men-from-applying-to-work-abroad/103804900>
3. Achtiar DSN, Budiarti I. The effects of transformational leadership and perceived organizational support on job and life satisfaction of preschool teachers. *International Information Institute Journal*. 2018;21:1301–1320.
4. Ali W. A review of situational leadership theory and relevant leadership styles: options for educational leaders in the 21st century. *Journal of Advances in Social Science and Humanities*. 2017;11(3).
5. Aung RK. Myanmar: a country of cultural diversity. *Radio Veritas Asia* [Internet]; c2020. Available from: <https://www.rvasia.org/myanmar-country-cultural-diversity>
6. Broyles AT. Principal laissez-faire leadership on teacher turnover: a look at the role gender has on teachers with different levels of experience [dissertation]. Arkansas: ProQuest; c2022.
7. Buitendach J. Job insecurity, extrinsic and intrinsic job satisfaction and affective organisational commitment of maintenance workers in a parastatal. *South African Journal of Business Management*. 2005;36(2).
8. Colquitt JA, LePine JA, Wesson MJ. *Organizational Behavior*. 5th ed. New York: McGraw-Hill Education; c2015.
9. Delgado ML. Democratic leadership in middle schools of Chihuahua, Mexico: improving middle schools through democracy. *Journal of International Education and Leadership*. 2014;4(1).
10. Deloitte. Dominant leaders: more harmful than helpful? Deloitte Insights [Internet]. c2022. Available from: <https://action.deloitte.com/insight/2356/dominant-leaders-more-harmful-than-helpful>
11. Emery CR, Barker KJ. The effect of transactional and transformational leadership styles on the organizational commitment and job satisfaction of customer contact personnel. *Journal of Organizational Culture, Communications and Conflict*. 2007;11(1):77.
12. Febres GE. Relationship between transactional leadership styles, transformational leadership style and subordinates' job satisfaction [dissertation]. Arizona: ProQuest; c2017.
13. Fiaz SI, Su Q. Leadership styles and employees' motivation: perspective from an emerging economy. *Journal of Developing Areas*. 2017;51(4):143–156.
14. Global Knowledge Index. Knowledge for all. Knowledge4All [Internet]; c2023. Available from: <https://www.knowledge4all.com/country->

- profile?CountryId=1077
15. Govender G, Lasrado F. Leadership style and job satisfaction: a developing economy perspective. *Corporate Ownership and Control*. 2013;10(4).
 16. Hamzah NAB, Mohd IM. The relationship between headmaster's instructional leadership practices and teacher's job satisfaction. In: *Proceedings of the 2nd Padang International Conference on Educational Management and Administration 2021*. Padang; c2022. p. 135–149.
 17. Hoque K, Zohir T. Relationship between principals' leadership styles and teachers' behavior. *Behavioral Sciences*. 2023;13(2):111.
 18. International Trade Administration. Burma private education law. International Trade Administration [Internet]; c2023. Available from: <https://www.trade.gov/market-intelligence/burma-private-education-law>
 19. Iqbal AF, Akhtar M. Relationship between teachers' job satisfaction and students' academic performance. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*. 2016;(65):335–344.
 20. Lee S. The style of democratic leadership. *Torch* [Internet]; c2023 [cited 2024 Feb 20]. Available from: <https://torch.io/blog/what-is-democratic-leadership/>
 21. Loeb H, Knapp MS. New thinking about instructional leadership. *Phi Delta Kappan*. 2010;92(3):66–69.
 22. Malec M. Autocratic leadership: a guide for workplace management. *Learnerbly* [Internet]; c2022. [cited 2024 Feb 11]. Available from: <https://www.learnerbly.com/articles/autocratic-leadership>
 23. Martins J. Before you try transactional leadership, read this. *Asana* [Internet]; c2023 [cited 2024 Feb 19]. Available from: <https://asana.com/resources/transactional-leadership>
 24. MetLife. The MetLife survey of the American teacher: challenges for school leadership. *MetLife* [Internet]; c2012 [cited 2024 Feb 3]. Available from: <https://metlife-prod-2019.adobecqms.net/about-us/newsroom/2013/february/the-metlife-survey-of-the-american-teacher--challenges-for-school/>
 25. Northouse PG. *Leadership: Theory and Practice*. 6th ed. Thousand Oaks (CA): SAGE Publications; c2012.
 26. Oh JKD, Kim DK. The impact of inclusive leadership and autocratic leadership on employees' job satisfaction and commitment in sport organizations: the mediating role of organizational trust and the moderating role of sport involvement. *MDPI*. 2023;15(4):1–13.
 27. Oravee Z, Kusa R. Job satisfaction and employee performance in Nasarawa State Water Board, Lafia, Nigeria. *Revista CIMEXUS*. 2018;8(2).
 28. Radio Free Asia Burmese. Myanmar's education sector under strain. *Radio Free Asia* [Internet]; c2023. [cited 2024 Feb 2]. Available from: <https://www.rfa.org/english/news/myanmar/education-sector-03072023171459.html>
 29. Goddard R, Goddard Y, Kim ES, Miller R. A theoretical and empirical analysis of the roles of instructional leadership, teacher collaboration, and collective efficacy beliefs in support of student learning. *American Journal of Education*. 2015;121(4):501–530.
 30. Hassan RB, Yahya JAY. Instructional leadership in Malaysia. *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology*. 2019;8(6S3).
 31. Sadasa K. The influence of organizational culture, leadership behavior, and job satisfaction towards teacher job performance. *Indian Journal of Health and Wellbeing*. 2013;4:1637–1642.
 32. Scott D. *Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation of elementary teachers* [thesis]. Texas: University of Texas at Tyler; c2017.
 33. Soe TK, Htun K. New rules for private schools. *Frontier Myanmar* [Internet]; c2018. [cited 2024 Feb 12]. Available from: <https://www.frontiermyanmar.net/en/new-rules-for-private-schools/>
 34. Stout S. Eight factors that make a school international. *Canisius Campus* [Internet]; c2022. [cited 2024 Feb 10]. Available from: <https://canisiuscampus.net/8-factors-that-make-a-school-international/>
 35. United Nations Conference on Trade and Development. Least developed countries list. UNCTAD [Internet]; c2023. [cited 2024 Feb 11]. Available from: <https://unctad.org/topic/least-developed-countries/list>
 36. World Family Education. International school curriculum options. *World Family Education* [Internet]; c2024. [cited 2024 Feb 11]. Available from: <https://worldfamilyeducation.com/international-school-curriculum-options/>

Creative Commons (CC) License

This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0) license. This license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.